

EFFECT OF FIBER DOSAGE ON THE MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF FIBER REINFORCED CONCRETE INTERFACE

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ABSTRACT

The interface between steel fiber and concrete has been deemed as an independent phase to find out the effect of steel fiber dosage on fiber reinforced concrete (FRC) bond-slip performance by laboratory experiment and numerical simulation. Single steel bar pull-out experiment had been conducted to investigate the effect of fiber dosage on the bond-slip performance between the steel bar and FRC with various steel fiber dosages. The experiment result shows that the bonding strength of SFRC was improved when the fiber dosage increased. Meanwhile, the numerical simulation method had been adopted to simulate mechanical properties of the interface by using RFPA^{2D} (Realistic Failure Process Analysis), through which the failure process of the steel bar pulled out from the FRC matrix under drawing load had been studied in details. This is a gradual process in which microscopic damages initiated, propagated and finally the slip appeared. Acoustic Emission (AE) events obtained from numerical simulation also help for understanding the damage process and the failure mechanism. From the analysis, the pull-out failure process could be divided into four stages, which are micro-slide stage, nonlinear stage, descent stage and residual stage, respectively, based on load-displacement curves.

1 INTRODUCTION

Metal fiber, non-metallic inorganic fiber or natural organic fiber have been widely applied in FRC for many years [1-3]. The reliable bond between the steel bar and the concrete matrix is the basis to guarantee a successful reinforced effect [4, 5]. To understand the bond stress distribution on the interface and its failure mechanism are of great significance in engineering [6].

In this paper, center pullout tests [7] had been carried out to investigate the process of a plain round bar being pulled out. Meanwhile, AE receivers has also been installed to monitor the whole process. The bond-slip characteristic performance of the steel bar being pulled out from FRC matrix with different dosages had been studied in details. Furthermore, by using RFPA^{2D} numerical models had been generated in which the steel bar, concrete matrix, the steel fiber and the interface between the steel bar and the concrete have been applied with corresponding parameters. The mechanical properties of each material phase were randomly allocated according to Weibull distribution [8]. Then, then whole process of single steel bar being pulled out including the crack initiation, extension and damage could be reproduced in the numerical model.

2 LABORATORY EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Specimen preparation

Mixing of steel fibres would improve the mechanical properties of concrete [9] and also the drawing performance. To prepare the specimen, C30 concrete had been used with its mix proportion shown in the following Table 1.

Cement (kg/m ³)	Water (kg/m ³)	Sand (kg/m ³)	Gravel (kg/m ³)	Water- cement ratio
461	175	512	1252	0.38

Table 1: Concrete Matrix.

Fiber type	Length (mm)	Diameter (mm)	L/D	Density (g/cm)	Tensile Strength (MPa)
Steel	35	1	65	7.85	600

Table 2: Steel Fiber.

The fiber dosages for the prepared specimen are 0, 1.0%, 1.2% and 1.5%, respectively. Four group specimens are labelled with NC and SFRC-1.0 to 1.5, respectively. In addition, six cubic specimens with the dimension of 100mm had been prepared for each group. All specimens were maintained under the natural atmosphere for 28 days. The whole experiment procedure was following the *Standard for test method of mechanical properties on ordinary concrete* [10]. Meanwhile, AE transducers and receivers had also been installed as per requirement.

2.2 Apparatus

The SANS Electro-hydraulic servo universal testing machine and μ SAMOS AE receiver, used for this experiment, are shown in Fig. 1 and 2, respectively. Two AE transducers were installed on the side surfaces to collect AE signals. The threshold value of AE receiver was set to be 40dB and the time parameters of PDT, HDT and HLT were set to be 150 μ s, 300 μ s and 500 μ s, respectively [see 11-13].

Figure 1 SANS Electro-hydraulic servo universal testing machine

Figure 2 AE Transducers and Receiver

2.3 Experimental Results

2.3.1 Failure pattern and relative strength

It could identified from Fig.3 that major failure pattern is the bar pulled out (slipping failure).

Figure 3 Failure mode

The mean value of relative bonding strengths for each group of specimens are listed in Table 3.

Specimen Groups	Mean Value of Relative Bonding Strength (MPa)	Improvement (%)
NC	1	0
SFRC-1.0	1.13	13
SFRC-1.2	1.14	14
SFRC-1.5	1.25	25

Table 3 Relative Bonding Strength

2.3.2 AE results

AE counts of Group SFRC-1.0 is shown in Fig. 4. After the initial loading, a small amount of AE signals appeared with the micro-damages appearing; along with the load carried on, the concrete began to crack and the count peak came out in the AE count curve at about 12000; then the steel bar was partially pulled out from concrete and the AE signal was not stable; finally the steel bar was fully pulled out from the concrete and the AE count reached to 0.

Figure 4 AE Counts during pullout SFRC-1.0

3 NUMERICAL SIMULATION RESULTS

Different to experimental specimens, five numerical specimens had been established (see Fig. 5). Same dimension has been adopted, *i.e.* the steel bar is 6mm in diameter and 30mm deep buried inside the concrete block. The fibre dosages of five specimens are 0, 0.5%, 1.0%, 1.2% and 1.5%, respectively, also labelled with NC, SFRC-0.5, 1.0, 1.2 and 1.5.

Figure 5 Numerical Model

3.1 The damage failure process

The pullout processes of the steel bars being pulled out from the normal concrete and SFRC-1.0 are shown in Fig. 6.

Figure 6 Pullout processes of NC and SFRC-1.0

As shown in Fig. 6, when the steel bar was pulled out, the crack appeared at the embedding top initially. When the loading is increased, the interface cells between the steel bar and the FRC matrix began to debond partially and the crack extended to a certain direction simultaneously. Then the macro-crack appeared on the embedding top and the crack extended continuously. Finally the interface debonded fully and the steel bar was pulled out from the concrete matrix. For NC specimen the failure cells appeared in a relative large zone near the embedding end while such failure cells are seldom for the FRC specimens.

The load- displacement curves of these five specimens are shown in Fig. 7. It could be concluded that the failure process could be divided into four stages, which are micro-slide stage, nonlinear stage, descent stage and residual bonding stage.

Figure 7 Load vs. displacement curves of pullout tests

3.2 Numerical results and discussions

Under loading condition, the load-displacement curves and the AE counts - time curves had some certain corresponding relation. The curves of the NC and SFRC specimens are shown Fig. 8:

Figure 8 Calculated load-displacement and AE counts

For the NC specimen, the peak loading values and the AE counts on the stress descent stage are less than those of SFRC-1.0. With the steel fibres added into the concrete matrix, the crack resistance and the ductility of the concrete had been enhanced and have its influence on the pullout process.

The toughness is a significant index to evaluate the energy-dissipating capacity and the plastic yielding ability before failure. The better is the material's toughness, the brittle failure may not happen. The pullout toughness was defined in the paper that the area enclosed by the load-displacement curve under rectangular coordinate [14]. The toughness calculated by the steel bar being pulled out from the normal concrete was set up as the base value 1. Then the toughness relative values of SFRC were calculated in Table 4. It was concluded that the toughness was increased when the fiber dosages increased. The corresponding relative pullout toughness value was 10.88%, 20.45%, 33.66% and 27.69%, respectively, corresponding to each specimen.

The SFRC relative maximum bond strength has been compared with the NC specimen in Table 4. Compared with the results of the experimental results (See Table 3), the variation trends are similar to each other, *i.e.* the bond strength was increased with the fiber dosage increased.

Concrete	The Relative Maximum Bond Strength	The Relative Pullout Toughness
NC	1	1
SFRC-0.5	1.0267	1.1088
SFRC-1.0	1.0670	1.2045
SFRC-1.2	1.1626	1.3366
SFRC-1.5	1.2004	1.2769

Table 4 Relative bond strengths and relative toughness of the pullout specimens

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the whole failure process of the steel rebar pulled out from the concrete matrix has been studied by using both experimental and numerical methods. All failure patterns in tested specimens are slipping ones, *i.e.* rebar had been pulled out from the concrete matrix. It could be observed that the pullout toughness had been increased along with the fiber dosage. Furthermore, the AE counts curves are highly correlated with the load-displacement curve. On the other hand, the results obtained from the numerical analysis are similar to the experimental tests and it shall be convenient to conduct more complicated study in this field. In the future, calibration works will be conducted and more numerical simulations could be expected to study the effect of fiber dosage in more details.

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